

CENTRAL ASIA AND GERMANY: GOALS AND PROSPECTS FOR COOPERATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12632914>

Germany and Central Asia might benefit much from cooperation on both fronts from a strategic perspective. Germany is among the major economic powers in Europe, while Central Asia boasts abundant natural resources, a strategic location, and a rich historical legacy. These allies share interests in today's globe, including advancing trade, bolstering political stability, battling terrorism and extremism, and collaborating in the fields of research and education.

German interest in Central Asia has increased dramatically in recent years due to major geopolitical upheavals as well as the region's expanding economic and political possibilities.

It is important to note that German foreign policy towards Central Asia is carried out in two directions. First, German foreign policy is closely linked to European regional strategy. The country was once the developer of the European Union Strategy for Central Asia, which was adopted back in 2007 and subsequently revised in 2019. Second, Germany is methodically carrying out its specific mandates in the area, which includes, above all, defending the rights of minority groups that speak German.

The latest high-level summits and visits involving German leadership, including visits by Federal President Frank-Walter Steinmeier to Uzbekistan took place in May 2019, and to Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan in June 2023,[5] visits by German Foreign Minister Annalena Bärbock took place in Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan in October 2022,[6] the EU-Central Asia summits in Astana took place

in October 2022 and in Cholpon-Ata in June 2023[7], in addition, the first conference on EU-Central Asia relations was successfully held in November 2022 in Samarkand[8] - all this points to an active dialogue between Germany and Central Asia.

During the visit from September 29 to 30, 2023 in Berlin, the leaders of the Central Asian countries held negotiations with the Chancellor and the President of Germany, and also took part in a joint business meeting from the Eastern Committee of the German Economy. At the business meeting, the parties agreed to draw up the “Berlin List” of multilateral projects in Central Asia, which will be jointly implemented [9].

More than 10 billion euros have been invested in Central Asia by German businesses to date, generating over 35,000 employees. Approximately 900 businesses with German funding currently manufacture goods and provide services in the area. Numerous other German businesses also indicated interest in working with Central Asia during the visit [1].

Berlin's foreign policy in Central Asia mainly concentrates on a number of themes, including addressing concerns associated with Afghanistan, fostering economic development with a focus on German goods and services, etc.

Germany, which has one of the most developed economies in the world, together with the rest of the EU countries, became Central Asia's third largest trading partner in 2010, behind only Russia and China. And in subsequent years, Germany's economic interests in the region grew dynamically. As a result, in 2021, Uzbekistan and the EU had \$3.8 billion in trade turnover, with Germany accounting for 25% of that sum. Additionally, there has been a growth in Uzbekistan's exports of goods to Germany and in bilateral trade.

Germany rose to prominence as the EU's top trading and economic partner in 2022, making up about 26% of all commerce between Uzbekistan and the EU. Of the total volume of investments received in Uzbekistan from the European Union in 2021, about 60% were investments from Germany, reaching almost \$5.5 billion. In turn, the government of the country supports Uzbekistan's accession to

the World Trade Organization (WTO) and the early signing of the Enhanced Partnership and Cooperation Agreement with the European Union. Germany's share of world trade rose during this period from 2.2% to 2.3%, total exports increased from 0.3% to 0.5%, and total imports fell from 4.1% to 3.5% [12].

All of the above suggests that over the past six years, Uzbek-German relations have been developing at a rapid pace. Germany is among the ten largest partner countries of Uzbekistan in foreign trade and ranks 7th with a share of 2.3% of total trade turnover after China (18.8), Russia (18.2), Kazakhstan (9.1), Turkey (6.8), the Republic of Korea (5.1) and Kyrgyzstan (2.4). The two countries' commercial turnover has expanded by 2.2 times over the years due to their collaborative efforts. (from almost \$530 million to 1.2 billion) [2].

The following are the main areas of collaboration today: peace and social cohesion; climate and energy; "just transition" (towards a climate-friendly economic system); employment and training; health; social security and population policy, etc.

As part of the status of a beneficiary of the Generalized System of Preferences "GSP+" granted by the EU, Uzbekistan exports fresh and dried fruits, vegetables, nuts, tomatoes, textile products, ready-made clothes, and certain industrial commodities to Germany. "GSP+" status provides for the application of a reduced tariff on a wide range of goods of more than 6 thousand items that can be supplied to the markets of EU countries [3].

At the invitation of the Federal President of Germany Frank-Walter Steinmeier, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev visited this country on May 2-3, 2023 [10].

In addition, a deal was made to establish a platform for communication between Germany and the Central Asian states during Sh. Mirziyoyev's May 2023 visit to Germany. In general, during the visit, 16 intergovernmental and interdepartmental documents were signed in the fields of economics, trade, finance, education, science and innovation [11].

Without exaggeration, it can be stated that the visit of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to Germany became a breakthrough in the modern history of our countries as well as a new stage in bilateral relations.

For cooperative projects and efforts to be implemented successfully, communication between the governments, corporate sectors, governmental agencies, and educational institutions of both nations must grow. Development that is both long-term and mutually beneficial can only be accomplished via cooperation and partnership.

Thus, cooperation between Central Asia and Germany has broad prospects and opportunities for deepening interaction in various fields. It is important to continue to actively develop and expand partnerships, striving to create stable and mutually beneficial relations between these regions.

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